

Analysis of the Influence of the Company's Internal Environment and the External Environment of the Company on Accountant Professional Code of Conduct

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received: 2 February 2022

Revised: 12 March 2022

Accepted: 20 April 2022

Key words: *Company's Internal Environment, Company's External Environment, Accountant Professional Code of Conduct*

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of the company's internal environment and the company's external environment on the code of ethics for the accountant profession. The research problems are as follows: Does the company's internal environment and the company's external environment affect the code of ethics for the accountant profession? The purpose of this study is to determine whether the company's internal environment and the external environment of the company affect the code of ethics for the accountant profession. This study examined 35 respondents by giving them a questionnaire before collecting data. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression statistical analysis and uses the T test to analyze the closeness of the relationship between individual variables, while testing the instrument using validity and reliability tests. The results of the analysis show that the company's internal environment and the company's external environment have no positive effect on the code of ethics for the accounting profession.

1. INTRODUCTION

Professional ethics is a topic of discussion that is being discussed in today's society. The lack of public concern for this multidimensional phenomenon has awakened Indonesians to prioritizing ethical behavior, because from the past until now the multidimensional crisis of ethical behavior has been neglected (Dania et al. 2019). Ethics is an important requirement for all professions, so one should not engage in unlawful behavior (Nuha, Miqdad, dan Sulistiyo 2021).

As members of the accounting profession are also responsible for maintaining the highest standards of ethical behavior in the organization, the public profession and themselves accountants have a responsibility to be competent and

maintain integrity and objectivity (Sulistiyo, Al Ardi, dan Roziq 2020). Obligation to maintain standards of ethical behavior.

This is related to the role of society in the accounting profession, especially in coaching the performance of public accountants (Hadi, Wardayati, dan Miqdad 2020). Those who use professional services need professional accountants. The professional label here symbolizes pride, commitment to quality, dedication to the interests of the customer and a sincere desire to help customers deal with problems so that the profession can become the trust of society (Hidayatullah, Wardayati, dan Roziq 2021).

In carrying out their professional duties, an accountant must comply with accounting ethics.

The accountant code of ethics is a norm of ethics or behavior that regulates the relationship between accountants and clients, between accountants and colleagues, and between professions and the wider community (Sihwahjoeni dan Gudono 2000).

According to Mulyadi (2002), professional ethics that have been published by bodies regulating professional ethics aims to regulate the behavior of their members in carrying out their duties in society and professional ethics of accounting practice in Indonesia is called a code of ethics and is issued by the Indonesian Accountants Association as an accounting professional organization. The Indonesian Institute of Accountants (IAI) formulated a code of ethics for the accounting industry for the first time in Indonesia at the 1973 conference. This code of ethics was later revised at the IAI conferences in 1981 and 1986, and then amended again at the IAI conferences in 1990, 1994, and 1998.

Under the auspices of this industry, accounting positions itself as a seller of services. Therefore, accountants are required to have high technical mastery knowledge and be able to apply the standards issued by professional associations (Code of Ethics, SAK and SPAP). At least every member of the profession must meet these standards, because with these standards accountants can maintain their technical and professional skills in the field of sales services, accountants are not only experts, but also must be able to carry out their professional work seriously or appropriately. And always comply with the standards that have been applied (Fachmi, Puspita, dan Prasetyo 2021).

Regarding the professional level, the accounting profession is required to have knowledge, skills and character. Character shows the values a person has, and these values are reflected in the attitudes and moral behavior he has, and the attitude and moral behavior of accountants will greatly determine the trust of society as users of their services Khomsiyah and Indriantoro (1997) argue that by maintaining integrity, accountants must act honestly, firmly,

and not objectively, while maintaining objectivity, accountants will act impartially without pressure or demands from certain parties or their personal interests.

The professional ability to understand and be sensitive in dealing with ethical problems is influenced by a person's work experience (Sularso dan Na'im 1999). One of the important requirements in obtaining permission to become an accountant is that work experience is observed to be a determining factor in predicting and observing the performance of public accountants (SK Menkeu No. 43/KMK. 017/1997). Logman believes in (Hartoko, Vandenbroucke, dan Vandewoude 1997) that experience is the achievement or increase of knowledge or skills for an activity or doing something for a long time.

Accounting major was born in the environment of accounting education. Education plays a very important role in the accounting printing industry. It is the seed of practitioners who are directly engaged in accounting. The birth of the accountant profession, from an accounting student to an accountant has never been separated from the education he received. Therefore, accounting education can be defined as the initial stage of accounting practice (Kustono 2021).

Based on the results of research that accounting students are currently rising accounting students, must have higher professional skills and levels, so they need to understand and understand the development of these disciplines accounting (Baihaqi, Setyanti, dan Irawan 2020).

Accounting educators and accounting students on Indonesian accounting ethics and revealed the adequacy of the content of college accounting courses. The results of the research hypothesis indicate that there are significant differences in cognition compared to accounting students, educational accountants have better cognition. Other results show that there is no significant difference between teaching accountants and teaching accountants who are also practitioners, in this field educational accountants tend to have better thinking. Researchers found that although some of the

subjects taught had ethical content, accounting education courses were still not sufficient to provide ethical rules for students to enter the world of work.

In this study, researchers will observe their views. Perception observation is based on the fact that perception is a person's direct response to something or someone's process of knowing something through the five senses ("Big Indonesian Dictionary"). Meanwhile, the observation of the concept of ethics is because the accounting profession is a profession whose activities are inseparable from activities related to ethics, so accountants must have a deep understanding of ethics as the standard of their profession.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Company Work Environment

The company's work environment is the company's social, psychological and physical life, which affects the performance of workers' duties (Masrohatin dan Tobing 2019). Human life is inseparable from the various conditions of the surrounding environment, where there is a very close relationship between humans and their environment (Prihatini et al. 2020). In this case, humans will always try to adapt to various circumstances in their surroundings. Likewise, employees working as humans cannot be separated from the various environments around the workplace (namely the work environment). During work, each employee will interact with various conditions in the work environment (Putra, Prihatini, dan Priyono 2020).

The work environment is the things around the worker that will affect their performance in carrying out the assigned tasks (Nitisemito 2002). In addition, according to (Sedarmayanti 2001), the work environment is all the tools and materials faced, the environment where a person works, how it works and personal and group work arrangements.

If humans can carry out activities as well as possible, healthy, safe and comfortable, it is said that the working conditions are good or appropriate. In the long term, it can be seen that the suitability of the work environment is in

addition to a work environment that is less conducive, requiring more manpower and time, and does not support the design of an effective work system (Sedarmayanti 2001).

The work environment is one of the factors that affect employee performance. Employees who work in a work environment that supports their best work will produce good performance, on the other hand, if employees work in a work environment that is less and does not support their best work, the employee concerned will become lazy and tired. Which causes low employee performance (Manora, Titisari, dan Syaharudin 2021).

Definition of the Company's Internal Environment

There are several factors that influence the accounting profession's code of ethics. Accountants will decide whether to perform productive work in accordance with working conditions, which will directly or indirectly affect the continuity of the organization. The internal work environment is a component that exists within an organization or company (Wardayati et al. 2019).

Definition of the Company's External Environment

The external work environment comes from outside the organization and has an influence on the organization, such as customers, third parties, colleagues, communities, government, and external groups (Mudawiyah, Prihatini, dan Wulandari 2019).

Organizations or companies should not only pay attention to the internal work environment of the organization, but must also be aware of the importance of the influence of the external work environment on employees or work performance, which will have an impact on the organization it manages (Abdurrasodik, Titisari, dan Yulisetiari 2020).

Accountant Professional Code of Ethics

Definition of Ethics

Ethics originated in ancient Greece. The singular form of the word "ethics" is "ethos" and

the plural is "*ta etha*". Ethos has many meanings, namely: ordinary residence, pasture, place of residence, habits / customs, morality, character, feelings, attitudes, ways of thinking. At the same time, the meaning of *ta etha* is habitual.

Therefore ethics is a science that discusses the quality of human behavior. Moreover, professional ethics who want to provide professional knowledge services to those in need, pay great attention to professional ethics .

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, ethics is knowledge about good and bad behavior, moral rights and obligations, a series of expectations or values related to morality; and values about the right or wrong behavior or behavior adopted by society. Ethics is the study of the study of thinking good and bad by paying attention to human behavior.

According to Aristotle, Aristotle divided the concept of ethics into two parts, namely Terminus Technicus and Manner and Custom. Terminus Technicus is ethics that is studied as the science of human behavior or behavior problems.

Definition of Profession

According to KBBI, professional: a field of work that is based on certain professional knowledge (skills, work, etc.) education. Professional: (a) related to work; (b) requires special skills to perform; (c) Payment terms). Professionalism is a professional or professional characteristic.

According to Wahid (2006), department is a person's conscious choice. The work that has been specially selected is carried out consistently and continuously. Therefore, you could say he was majoring in this field. Meanwhile, professionalism that supports his profession is the spirit, paradigm, spirit, behavior, thoughts, thoughts, and enthusiasm that continues to mature and improve his professional quality intellectually".

According to Wibowo (2015), professionals are the work of a small number of people who have special skills obtained through training or other experiences, or special skills acquired through both, so that professionals can guide or

provide advice/suggestions. You can also provide services to others in your field.

Definition of Professional Ethics

This kind of professional ethics plays an important role in the system of value norms, and professional rules, the system clearly states what is right or good for the profession and what is not right or bad for the profession. In other words, the goal of professional ethics is for professionals to act according to the rules and avoid behavior that is not in accordance with the professional code of ethics (Rizki, Titisari, dan Prihatini 2019).

According to Prakoso (2015), the definition of professional ethics is social ethics, in which special ethics is responsible for the knowledge and profession it carries. According to Suhendi and Zullanita (2016), the definition of professional ethics is an attitude of life that must meet the professional service needs of participating customers (customers) and professional knowledge, namely as a service in the context of obligations. Community is all members of society who need it accompanied by serious reflection. The definition of professional ethics is a certain professional code of ethics, so it must be understood correctly, not absolute ethics.

Definition of Code of Ethics

According to Article 43 of Law Number 20 of 2003, the code of ethics contains ethical norms and norms, and these norms and norms regulate the behavior of teachers in carrying out their professional duties. According to Fachmi et al. (2021) a code of ethics is a code of conduct that applies specifically to professionals in this field.

According to Soebekti (2006), professional ethics is in the form of norms and must be considered by those who carry out their professional duties.

Definition of the Accountant Professional Code of Ethics

Accounting plays an important role in increasing the transparency and quality of financial information. This is the condition for the realization of a healthy and efficient national

economy. In carrying out their duties, accountants must comply with the professional code of ethics. According to Bachtiar (2019), the ethics of the accounting profession is the science that discusses the good and bad behavior of an accountant. At the same time, people must understand jobs that require special training and knowledge.

There are eight accounting professional ethics listed in the Indonesian accountant code of ethics, as follows:

- Professional responsibilities

When carrying out professional duties, each member must use ethical and professional considerations in all activities carried out. Members should always be responsible for developing the accounting profession with other members. Must be able to maintain public trust and fulfill self-regulatory professional responsibilities. This requires the concerted efforts of all members to maintain and enhance the professional tradition (Eriandani dan Winarno 2021).

- Public interest

Every member of the accounting profession always acts in order to serve the community, uphold public trust and show professionalism. One of the characteristics is being responsible to the public (Prihatini et al. 2020). The accounting profession plays an important role in public society and in the accounting industry including customers, creditors, government, employers, employees, and others (Wijaya, Sulistyono, dan Roziq 2021). Rely on the objectivity and integrity of accountants in carrying out business functions. Public interest is defined as an organization that serves the public interest and its members as a whole (Kustono 2020). Dependency gives rise to attitudes and behavior of accountants when providing services that have an impact on the economic well-being of society and the country. The primary interest of the accounting profession is to make accountants understand that accounting services are provided at the highest level of achievement based on the ethical requirements needed to achieve that level of achievement (Mukti, Setyanti, dan Farida 2019).

- Integrity

To maintain and enhance public trust, each member must carry out their professional duties with high integrity. Honesty is an element of character and the basis of professional recognition. Integrity is the basis of public trust and a benchmark for members to examine their decisions. Here every member of the accounting profession is required to be honest without sacrificing the secrets of the recipient of his services.

- Objectivity

Each member maintains objectivity and has no conflict of interest in professional achievement. Objectivity is the quality that provides value to the services provided by members (Dania et al. 2019). The principle of activity demands that members be fair, impartial, rational, not prejudiced or biased. Members work in various capacities and must show objectivity in various situations. Members in public practice provide certification, taxation and management consulting services at the same time other members prepare financial reports as subordinates to provide internal audit services and work with their financial and management skills in industry, education and government.

- Competence and professional care

Each member shall perform his professional service with care, comment and be diligent and is obliged to maintain his professional knowledge and skills. This means that members are required to provide professional services to the best of their ability (Wijaya, Prasetyo, dan Kustono 2020). This is for the benefit of using the service and in line with the professional responsibilities of society. Competence acquired through members' education and experience should not portray themselves as having skills or experience they do not have (Novitasari, Hisamuddin, dan Maharani 2019).

- Confidentiality

Each member must respect the confidentiality of information obtained during professional service, and may not use or disclose this information without consent (Wirawan, Prihatini, dan Sudaryanto 2019). Unless there is a

professional or legal problem or obligation to disclose. Professional standards relating to confidentiality define guidelines as to the nature and extent of the obligation of confidentiality. It also addresses various situations where information obtained in the course of performing professional service can or should be disclosed. Members are required to respect the confidentiality of information about services or companies obtained through their professional services (Baihaqi et al. 2020).

- Professional behavior

Each member must behave consistent with a good professional reputation and avoid actions that could discredit the profession (Rizki et al. 2019).

- Technical standards

Each member must carry out his professional services in accordance with technical standards and professional standards in accordance with his expertise (Bektiarso et al. 2021). Members are required to carry out the assignment from the service recipient as long as the assignment is in line with the principles of integrity and objectivity (Almira, Sularso, dan Setyanti 2021). Standards that must be adhered to for the accounting profession are standards issued from:

1. Indonesian Accountants Association
2. International Federation of Accountants
3. Regulatory bodies
4. Relevant laws and regulations

- Accountants' skills

There are several skills an accountant must have, namely:

1. Accounting theory
2. Cost accounting
3. Auditing
4. Accounting system
5. Taxation
6. Management information system
7. Financial accounting
8. The economy of the company

The Importance of Professional Code of Ethics

There are many reasons for the need to develop a code of conduct. Ludigdo (2007) explain some of the reasons are:

1. The code of ethics is a way to improve the organizational atmosphere so that individuals can adhere to the code of conduct.
2. Because of the help system, ethical people are needed, the market is not sufficient to guide organizational behavior to consider the ethical implications of any business decisions.
3. Companies need a code of ethics to determine the company's status as a profession, and a code of ethics is one of the signs.
4. The code of ethics is also seen as an effort to institutionalize the ethics and values of the company's founders, so that the code of conduct becomes part of the company culture and helps to integrate new individuals into that culture.

Professional values can also be called ethical principles. Chung and Megginson (1981) put forward four moral principles, namely:

- a. Respect for dignity and dignity
- b. Caring and responsible
- c. Integrity in relationships
- d. Responsibility to society

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

Based on the theory outlined these thoughts can be clarified through the influence of the company's internal environment and the company's external environment on the code of ethics for the accountant profession.

Figure 1. Research Design

Data Type and Sources

The data used in this study are primary data. The primary data collection method is done through an online questionnaire where

respondents can access and fill out the online questionnaire through the questionnaire link that has been distributed.

Population and Sample

The population of this study were 35 students of S1 Accounting University of Jember, Class of 2018. The sample selection method used is a non-randomly sampling method based on quota sampling).

Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method was carried out with the help of the SPSS program. SPSS is a computer software whose function is to calculate statistical data.

Data Quality Test

a. Validity test

If the data collection tool can and can reveal data or information from the variables studied, and can measure research expectations, then it is effective. The testing technique uses a significance level of 5% to determine the strength of the influence between the independent and dependent variables. Based on the output below, the number of each question item produced is less than 0.05, so that all research tools used are considered effective.

Table 1. Validity Test

Variable	Q	Sig. (2-tailed)	Description
Accountant Professional Code of Ethics	No. 1	0,005	Valid
	No.2	0	Valid
	No. 3	0,002	Valid
	No. 4	0,004	Valid
	No. 5	0,004	Valid
	No. 6	0,001	Valid
	No. 7	0,009	Valid
	No. 8	0,01	Valid
	No. 9	0,011	Valid
	No. 10	0,015	Valid

	No. 11	0,043	Valid
	No. 12	0,003	Valid
	No. 13	0,003	Valid
	No. 14	0	Valid
	No. 15	0,003	Valid
	No. 16	0	Valid
	No. 17	0	Valid
	No. 18	0	Valid
	No. 19	0.003	Valid
	No. 20	0	Valid
	No. 21	0	Valid
	No. 22	0,023	Valid
Company Internal Environment	No. 23	0,001	Valid
	No. 24	0,001	Valid
	No. 25	0	Valid
	No. 26	0,03	Valid
	No. 27	0,001	Valid
	No. 28	0	Valid
	No. 29	0	Valid
	No. 30	0,004	Valid
	No. 31	0.025	Valid
	No. 32	0.001	Valid
	No. 33	0.001	Valid
Company External Environment	No. 34	0.001	Valid
	No. 35	0.001	Valid
	No. 36	0.002	Valid
	No. 37	0.037	Valid

No. 38	0.006	Valid
No. 39	0.035	Valid
No. 40	0	Valid
No. 41	0,007	Valid

b. Reliability Test

If the data collection tool can be used to measure variables repeatedly, and can produce the same or slightly changed information or data, then the data collection tool is considered reliable. If the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.07, then the data is reliable. Based on the output below, the number generated for each item is > 0.07, so it can be said that all the research tools used are reliable.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Variable	Q	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Accountant Professional Code of Ethics	No. 1	0.926	Reliable
	No.2	0.925	Reliable
	No. 3	0.926	Reliable
	No. 4	0.926	Reliable
	No. 5	0.926	Reliable
	No. 6	0.925	Reliable
	No. 7	0.928	Reliable
	No. 8	0.927	Reliable
	No. 9	0.928	Reliable
	No. 10	0.928	Reliable
	No. 11	0.929	Reliable
	No. 12	0.926	Reliable
	No. 13	0.925	Reliable
	No. 14	0.925	Reliable

Company Internal Environment	No. 15	0.926	Reliable	
	No. 16	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 17	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 18	0.926	Reliable	
	No. 19	0.926	Reliable	
	No. 20	0.923	Reliable	
	No. 21	0.923	Reliable	
	No. 22	0.926	Reliable	
	No. 23	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 24	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 25	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 26	0.927	Reliable	
	No. 27	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 28	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 29	0.924	Reliable	
	No. 30	0.926	Reliable	
	No. 31	0.927	Reliable	
	No. 32	0.925	Reliable	
	No. 33	0.925	Reliable	
	Company External Environment	No. 34	0.924	Reliable
		No. 35	0.925	Reliable
No. 36		0.926	Reliable	
No. 37		0.926	Reliable	
No. 38		0.925	Reliable	
No. 39		0.926	Reliable	
No. 40		0.924	Reliable	
No. 41		0.925	Reliable	

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4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Multiple Linear Regression Test

In this study, the analytical tool used to simplify multiple regression calculations will use the SPSS tool, so that the results obtained from these calculations are as follows: The regression equation is obtained: $Y = 340.261 - 0.735X_1 - 1.251X_2$.

Table 3. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	
		B	Std. Error
1	(Constant)	340.261	143.43
	Internal Environment	-0.735	0.984
	External Environment	-1.251	0.797

b. Inner Model Evaluation

Table 4. Test the Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square
1	.580 ^a	.337

As can be seen from the table above, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.580. This shows that there is a strong relationship between the independent variable (company internal environment and company external environment) and the dependent variable (accounting code of ethics).

It can be seen from the table above that the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.337 or 33.7%. This means that the internal environment variable (X₁) and the external environment (X₂) can explain the accounting students' understanding of the accounting profession ethics

(Y) by 33.7%, while the remaining 67.3% is explained by other variables that are not included. In research.

c. F Test (Simultaneous)

This test is done to find out whether the independent variable is. The steps are as follows:

H₀: Collectively, the company's internal environment and the company's external environment have no effect on the code of ethics for the accountant profession.

H₁: Jointly the company's internal environment and the company's external environment have an effect on the code of ethics for the accountant profession.

Table 5. F-Test (simultaneous)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	845.064	2	422.532	1.524	.292 ^b
	Residual	1663.158	6	277.193		
	Total	2508.222	8			

Based on data analysis of 35 accounting students, the multiple regression equation of the company's internal environment (X₁) and the company's external environment (X₂) on the accounting professional code of ethics (Y) is as follows:

$$Y = 340,261 - 0.735X_1 - 1,251X_2$$

The overall multiple regression coefficient value is negative, this means that if the value of the two independent variables in the form of the internal environment and the external environment increases or is increased. The accounting students' understanding of the accounting professional code of ethics will decrease.

The negative value of the regression coefficient of each variable is studied, meaning that if one of the independent variables is added by one unit it will reduce the value of accounting

students' understanding of the accounting professional code of ethics with the assumption that the other variables are constant.

From the analysis, the calculated F value is 1.524 while F table is 3.28 at significant $\alpha = 0.05$, then F count > F table (1.524 < 3.28), this means that together the independent variables (internal environment and external environment) have no effect. Significant effect on the understanding of accounting students about the code of ethics of the accounting profession.

So the first hypothesis which states that it is assumed that the internal work environment and the external work environment together have a significant influence on accounting students' understanding of the accounting profession code of ethics is rejected.

d. T test (partial)

Table 6. T test (partial)

Model	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	2.372	0.055		
	Internal Environment	-0.747	0.483	1	1
	External Environment	-1.568	0.168	1	1

Based on the value of the output data on the coefficients, it is known that the significance value (Sig.) Is 0.55 while the significance value is $\alpha = 0.05$, so the output significance is greater than α significance (0.55 > 0.05). This means that together the independent variables (internal environment and external environment) do not have a significant effect on accounting students' understanding of the accounting professional code of ethics.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

In this study, the population was 35 undergraduate students in accounting. Of the independent variables studied in undergraduate accounting students, the variables of the internal work environment and the external work environment together have a negative and significant effect on the code of ethics of the accounting profession. Thus the second hypothesis in this study is accepted where it is suspected that the company's internal environment and the company's external environment have no effect on the code of ethics of the accountant profession.

Based on the results obtained, the authors propose suggestions that might be useful for the company in dealing with accountants, namely by minimizing the internal and external work environments of the company that has the potential to affect accountants' professionalism.

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